

Economic Diversity of the ASEAN Countries

Louangrath, P.I. ★

About the author

★Louangrath, P.I. is an Assistant Professor in Business Administration at Bangkok University, Bangkok, Thailand. He could be reached by email at: Lecturepedia@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research examines economic identity of the ASEAN countries. It is proved that the ASEAN is a heterogeneous group lacking common economic identity. The method used in this research involves series of statistical tests. The data is comprised of economic data from the IMF's World Economic Outlook 2013. Four main economic issues are used: per capita GDP from 2004 to 2013, GDP growth rates from 2004 to 2013, HDI-2013 for ASEAN member countries, and Gini coefficient. Following the Dixon and Damgaard's approach, the Gini coefficient for the ASEAN region was calculated. The Anderson-Darling tests proved that the per capita GDP among the member countries are not normally distributed. This finding points to the lack of homogeneity within the group. Secondly, the paired means difference analysis of the per capita GDP and the GDP growth rates confirmed that there is a significant difference among the ASEAN countries. Thirdly, the HDI for 2013 shows significant difference among the ten countries ($t_d = 2.68$). While the Gini coefficient for the individual countries ranges from 35 to 47, the Gini coefficient for the ASEAN group is about 65. The Laplace trend test for 2004 to 2013 shows that there is a significant trend narrowing the gap of the regional Gini coefficient ($Z_{Laplace} = 3.38$). The Weibull regression also shows a negatively slope for ASEAN's Gini coefficient year-by-year trend. This research confirms that the ASEAN countries do not have a common economic identity. The empirical fact would make market integration under AEC-2015 a great challenge for stakeholders.

Key words: AEC-2015, Anderson-Darling test, ASEAN heterogeneity, economic identity, Gini coefficient, Human Development Index (HDI), Laplace trend test, and Weibull distribution.

CITATION:

Louangrath, P.I. (2015). "Economic Diversity of the ASEAN Countries." *Inter. J. Res. Methodol. Soc. Sci.*, Vol., 1, No. 2: pp. 48-60. (Apr. – Jun. 2015).

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This paper asserts that there is an economic diversity among the ASEAN countries. Diversity is defined as differences in identity. We based the identity of the ASEAN countries on two economic indicators: GDP and HDI. Identity is defined as a sense of belonging. (Lee, 2000, p. 29). The shared sentiment among group members may be created on the basis on shared descent, language, sanctuaries, and customs (Leoussi and Grosby, 2006, p. p. 115). Common identity may be seen

through ethnicity (Wallman, 1977, pp. 531-532). Some writers explained identity on the basis of nationalism (Rothi, 2005, pp. 135-155; and Miller, 1995). The introduction of the AEC-2015 introduces unique form of social identity. This new identity transcends national border to include 10 countries in the ASEAN region. The AEC wants to create a regional community on the basis of cultural, educational and economic integration. This new identity transcends the traditional notion of self-concept in relations to a social group (Turner, 1986, p. 237-253). It involves the acculturation of more than six hundred million people into adopting the idea of shared ideal of “one vision, one identity, one community.”

Writers claimed that social identity is used as a means to manage intergroup behavior (Taifel and Turner, 1979, pp. 33-47, and Turner, 1999, p. 6-34). The goal of the AEC is economic integration; a creation of a common market. The creation of AEC’s shared vision, identity and community is a means to facilitate regional economic integration. This paper examines whether there is a shared identity on the basis of economics in this new community. Four main factors are used as indicators for economic identity: (i) per capita GDP, (ii) GDP growth rate, (iii) HDI and (iv) intra-regional Gini coefficient. Lacking economic homogeneity, market integration would face an up hill battle. From the European Union’s experience it was found that economic heterogeneity hinders the groups in realizing its full potential. (Hopner and Schafer, 2012, p. 19). In the proposed AEC, the blue print for integration exists. However, there are at least four countries: Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar and Vietnam, that are less developed in comparison to the other six original members. With economic heterogeneity, the AEC may repeat the EU’s experience. Part of the EU’s current financial crisis is the lack of economic homogeneity among group members.

The intended contribution of this research is to provide stakeholders with a new lens to look at the AEC. By verifying whether the AEC has an economic identity, stakeholders can better assess the probable outcome of policy implementation to achieve the goal of “one vision, one identity, one community.”

2.0 DATA

The data used in this research comes from the World Economic Outlook 2013 published by the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Relevant economic data for the ASEAN countries from 2004 to 2013 were separated for analysis. These data include: (i) per capita GDP, and (ii) annual GDP growth rate. Additional data, such as Human development Index (HDI) came from the annual statistics produced by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) for the year 2013. The Gini coefficient for the region was calculated using Dixon and Damgaard approach.

Table 1. Annual GDP of 10 countries in ASEAN

Country	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Brunei	79,302.82	82,567.71	83,659.61	82,052.74	80,221.21
Cambodia	2,459.64	2,646.49	2,840.40	3,055.27	3,280.68
Indonesia	8,432.70	8,973.56	9,554.34	10,108.43	10,661.63
Laos	4,382.25	4,761.36	5,153.34	5,576.56	6,022.04
Malaysia	20,335.84	21,498.39	22,742.22	23,630.68	25,088.81
Myanmar	3,678.78	3,932.90	4,262.68	4,655.78	5,074.26
Philippines	5,550.36	5,773.74	6,122.30	6,545.99	6,953.29
Singapore	70,657.26	75,113.21	77,690.83	81,647.56	85,227.12
Thailand	13,187.95	13,513.55	14,690.31	15,252.06	15,596.54
Vietnam	4,395.52	4,716.98	5,000.76	5,300.32	5,657.25

Source: <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/weo/2018/01/weodata/index.aspx>

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Series of statistical tests were employed in order to identify and verify economic identity of the ASEAN countries as a group. Firstly, the Anderson-Darling test was used to test data distribution. The Anderson-Darling test is a statistic defined to improve the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test in the test

of the distribution (Press, 1992, p. 621). It is a test used to confirm whether the data is normally distributed. Secondly, the paired means comparison study was used to verify the intra-group homogeneity among the ASEAN countries. This finding was verified by the paired t-test. The UNDP reports each country's HDI annually. This figured was used to determine whether the ten countries in the ASEAN are significantly different on the basis on HDI score. Group homogeneity on the basis of income distribution was also tested through Gini coefficient analysis. Finally, the Gini coefficient for the ASEAN was calculated over a period from 2004 to 2013. The Laplace trend test was use to verify the direction of the trend for the group's Gini coefficient. Throughout the tests, a confidence interval at 0.95 was used.

The economic data consists of 10 years from 2003 to 2014 inclusive. For purposes of minimum sample size, these ten years are considered adequate by using the Anderson-Darling test as the standard requiring $n > 5$. This 10 years period mirrors the period used for 10-years US treasury bond (O'Sullivan and Sheffrin, 2003, p. 197).

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The distribution of the data for the ten years covering the period between 2004 and 2013 was verified by the Anderson–Darling test. The Anderson-darling test is a statistic defined to improve the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test in the test of the distribution (Press, 1992, p. 621). The test statistics for the AD test is given by:

$$AD = -n - S \tag{1}$$

where n is the sample size and S is given by:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2i-1}{n} [\ln(F(Z)) + \ln(\ln(1 - F(Z)))] \tag{2}$$

The AD observed value may be adjusted by:

$$AD^* = AD \left(1 + \frac{0.752}{n} + \frac{2.25}{n^2} \right) \tag{3}$$

The theoretical value for the AD test at 95% confidence interval is 2.27

The result of the AD test is tabulated in Table 2. For the 10 years period, the GDP for the ASEAN countries are not normally distributed. We report the result of the AD test in two segments. First, the AD test result for the individual country's GDP between 2010 and 2014 (5 years period) is reported in Table 2. Second, the result of the AD test for the 10 countries as a group is reported in Table 3.

Table 2. Anderson-Darling test results for individual country GDP for FY2010-2014

Country	AD(obs)	AD*(95%)	Conclusion
Brunei	3.96	2.492*	Not normal
Cambodia	4.49	2.492	Not normal
Indonesia	4.37	2.492	Not normal
Laos	4.39	2.492	Not normal
Malaysia	4.40	2.492	Not normal
Myanmar	4.51	2.492	Not normal

Philippines	4.60	2.492	Not normal
Singapore	4.34	2.492	Not normal
Thailand	4.27	2.492	Not normal
Vietnam	4.37	2.492	Not normal

*See Appendix 1 for the theoretical value of the Anderson-Darling test.

The result of the Anderson-Darling test for the ASEAN as a single group for a period of 5 years shows that the distribution of the group’s GDP is not normal. The annual AD test result for each year is tabulated in Table 2. The result of the group’s non-normality of their GDP distribution leads us to speculate that the ASEAN countries are diverse. This diversity was later verified in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 2. Anderson-Darling test results for ASEAN 10 countries for FY2010-2014

ASEAN group	AD(obs)	AD*(95%)	Conclusion
FY2010	8.11	2.492	Not normal
FY2011	8.20	2.492	Not normal
FY2012	8.28	2.492	Not normal
FY2013	8.57	2.492	Not normal
FY2014	8.85	2.492	Not normal

The AD test is generally followed by the adjacency test in order to verify whether the data is a set of random events. The adjacency test is a tool to verify whether a data set is comprised of random numbers. (Bassein, 1996, pp. 482-490). Random number is defined as a number or string of numbers whose large set (i) creates or manifest an underlying distribution, and (ii) each number or element of the set is independent. Independent means that one number is not correlated to the successive number. The null hypothesis may be rejected if the test statistic lies outside of the lower and upper bound of the critical value. (Hart, 1942, pp. 445-7). The hypothesis statements are given by: $H_0 : L_{obs} < L_{0.05}$ and $H_A : L_{obs} > L_{0.05}$.

The critical value of L is given in a range of lower and upper value. If the test statistic value falls within this range, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Recall that the null hypothesis states that the pattern of the data is random. If the test statistic for the observation falls out of the range, i.e. lower than the lower bound or higher than the upper bound, the series is not random. The null hypothesis assumes random distribution. The purpose of the test is to reject this assumption. The null hypothesis is rejected if the observed value falls outside of the L-range. Adjacency test for randomness is accomplished by:

$$L_{n<25} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (X_{i+1} - X_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2} \tag{4}$$

There are ten countries in the ASEAN for five years period: $n = 5$. The null hypothesis value for the L-critical at 0.95 confidence interval is: $1.06 < L_{0.05} < 2.94$. The table below shows the result of the adjacency test for 10 countries in 5 years.

Table 3: Per Capita GDP of the ASEAN Countries are Random Events

Item	Year	L(obs)	L(0.05)	Result
------	------	--------	---------	--------

1	FY2010	0.000009	1.06 < L < 2.94	Not Random
2	FY2011	0.000010	1.06 < L < 2.94	Not Random
3	FY2012	0.000010	1.06 < L < 2.94	Not Random
4	FY2013	0.000009	1.06 < L < 2.94	Not Random
5	FY2014	0.000009	1.06 < L < 2.94	Not Random

The null hypothesis is rejected. The per capita GDP among the ASEAN countries are not normally distributed and are non-random numbers. These two findings points to the possibility of intra-group heterogeneity; this lack of homogeneity may be evidence for deeper issues and challenges facing the AEC-2015 regionalization and the new social identifier of “one vision, one identity and one community” in the economic sphere may not easily be achieved.

4.1 Per capita GDP and the GDP Growth Rates among the ASEAN Countries

The purpose of analyzing the per capita GDP is to verify whether there is an intra-ASEAN homogeneity. This test is accomplished through two statistical tests. Firstly, the paired mean analysis is accomplished by d-bar analysis test (Rubin, 1973, pp. 159-183; Anderson, 1980, pp. 61-66; and Kupper *et al.*, 1981, pp. 271-291). The d-bar analysis is given by:

$$t_d = \frac{\bar{d}}{S_d / \sqrt{n}} \quad (5)$$

Secondly, the conclusion reached in the d-bar analysis is verified by the paired t-test. (Goulden, 1956, pp. 50-55). These double-tests are used in order to avoid Type I error. The paired t-test is provided by:

$$T_{paired} = (\bar{X} - \bar{Y}) \sqrt{\frac{n(n-1)}{\sum (\hat{X}_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}} \quad (6)$$

Alternatively, the paired means T test may be calculated by:

$$T = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2) - (\mu_1 - \mu_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}} \quad (7)$$

The results of both tests are tabulated in Table 3 showing that there are significant difference among the ASEAN countries on the basis of per capita GDP and GDP growth rate. These findings show that there is a lack of homogeneity among the ASEAN countries.

Table 4: T value of paired Mean for Per Capita GDP of group and country

Country	FY2010	FY2011	FY2012	FY2013	FY2014
Brunei	5.39	5.39	5.21	5.16	5.11
Cambodia	(3.31)	(3.31)	(3.71)	(3.91)	(4.12)
Indonesia	(0.18)*	(0.18)*	(0.50)*	(0.65)*	(0.80)*
Laos	(1.77)	(1.77)	(2.14)	(2.31)	(2.49)
Malaysia	2.06	2.06	1.80	1.69	1.58*
Myanmar	(2.24)	(2.24)	(2.62)	(2.80)	(2.98)
Philippines	(1.30)*	(1.30)*	(1.66)	(1.82)	(1.99)
Singapore	5.27	5.27	5.08	5.04	4.99

Thailand	0.90*	0.90*	0.60 *	0.48 *	0.35*
Vietnam	(1.85)	(1.85)	(2.22)	(2.39)	(2.57)

*No significant difference from group mean.

The lack of homogeneity among the ASEAN countries may present greater challenges to the AEC-2015 integration. The idea of an ASEAN identity may become unrealistic. In order to minimize the intra-group difference on the basis of language, the ASEAN suggested the use of English as a common language. As for cultural and historical diversity within the group, ASEAN member countries celebrate its rich diversity. However, if the AEC should be a common market; ideally it should be economically homogeneous. Homogeneity in regional economies ensures equality among members and inclusivity of growth as a single market. However, since the 10 countries in the ASEAN are economically diverse, inclusive growth may be a challenge that is not easily overcome.

4.2 Human Development Index Trend among the ASEAN Countries

The second indicator of economic identity for the ASEAN countries is HDI. Human Development Index measures the impact of economic policies on the quality of life (Davies and Quinlivan, 2006, pp. 868-876). HDI is not a year-to-year indicator. For that reason, 2013 is used in this paper because it represents the latest figure for HDI measurement (McGillivray and White, 2006, pp. 183-192). The HDI from 2010 to 2014 for the ASEAN countries is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. HDI for ASEAN countries FY2010 - FY2014

Country	FY2010	FY2011	FY2012	FY2013	FY2014
Brunei	0.846	0.852	0.860	0.863	0.864
Cambodia	0.533	0.540	0.546	0.553	0.558
Indonesia	0.662	0.669	0.677	0.682	0.686
Laos	0.542	0.554	0.563	0.573	0.582
Malaysia	0.774	0.776	0.779	0.783	0.787
Myanmar	0.526	0.533	0.540	0.547	0.552
Philippines	0.669	0.666	0.671	0.676	0.679
Singapore	0.911	0.917	0.920	0.922	0.924
Thailand	0.720	0.729	0.733	0.737	0.738
Vietnam	0.655	0.662	0.668	0.675	0.678

The ASEAN are divided into two groups. The old ASEAN members have six countries: Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand. The second group with the new members consists of Cambodia, Laos, Myanmar, and Vietnam. Using the paired T test, using equation 7, we report the result of their significance of the difference in Table 6.

Table 6. Significance of difference in HDI for group 1 and group 2 in ASEAN

Country	FY2010	FY2011	FY2012	FY2013	FY2014
Mean1	0.76	0.77	0.77	0.78	0.78
μ_1	0.68	0.68	0.69	0.70	0.70
Var1	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Mean2	0.56	0.57	0.58	0.59	0.59
μ_2	0.51	0.51	0.52	0.53	0.54
Var2	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003
T(obs)	0.43	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.46
T*(95%)	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64	1.64
pValue	0.238	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22
Conclude	Not sig.				

*The procedure on how to calculate the pValue is given in Appendix 2.

The result of the calculation for the significant difference of HDI among countries in Table 6 shows that there is no significant difference in the 5 years period of the study. This finding is consistent with the findings of no significance in the GDP analysis.

As part of the new social identity intended by the AEC, social development is keyed. As a measurement of social development, HDI comparison helps stakeholder to see where member countries stand with respect to other group members. The above result shows that in terms of human development, the ASEAN countries have homogeneity. This finding further underscores the importance of common grounds for the 10 countries when it comes to economic identity for the group. It may be easy to promote market integration and a common market where member countries are on similar scale of development. The ideal of inclusive growth could be achieved if members of the group are uniform or similar in their development. This homogeneity in HDI does not call into question the vision of “one vision, one identity, one community.”

4.3 Intra-ASEAN Gini Coefficient as Evidence of Economic Heterogeneity

The fourth factor used to indicate economic identity for the ASEAN is the Gini coefficient. The Gini coefficient is the measure of statistical dispersion of income distribution within a population. A Gini coefficient with a value of 1.00 means a maximum inequality within the group. It was first proposed by Gini as a measure for income inequality (Gini, 1936). As a measure of inequality, Gini coefficient is widely used in various fields of social science (Sadras and Bongiovanni, 2004, pp. 303-310). Two approaches to Gini coefficient calculation are currently in use: unordered data and ranked data. Gini coefficient for unordered data:

$$G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |x_i - x_j|}{2n^2 \mu} \quad (8)$$

For increasing size (ascending order) data:

$$G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (2i - n - 1) \hat{x}_i}{n^2 \mu} \quad (9)$$

This paper adopts equation (9) to determine the regional Gini coefficient. In so doing, the current per capita income for each country is used. It is assumed that each country is an element of a group or population. The number of observation for ASEAN is: $n = 10$. For the period from 2004 to 2013, the Gini coefficients for the ASEAN group are: 0.70, 0.69, 0.69, 0.69, 0.67, 0.67, 0.67, 0.67, 0.66, 0.65 and 0.65 while for the individual countries, the Gini coefficient provided by the UNDP ranges from 0.35 to 0.47 for the year 2014. This discrepancy between country and region points to a potential development problem for the AEC.

If the Gini coefficient is used as an indicator of economic equality, domestically each country fairs better than being part of the AEC. A higher Gini coefficient among the group also implied that there are rich and poor countries within the proposed economic community. With unbalanced economic development in unequal income distribution, the ideal of “one vision, one identity, one community” presents a greater challenge to achieve. As for the concept of shared identity, the economic divide among member countries would hinder uniformity. This finding should alert concerns for stakeholders and policy makers in the AEC.

The result of equation (9) shows the gulf in income distribution. The Gini coefficient from 2010 to 2014 provides an adequate data for a trend test verifying whether there is an improving or deteriorating trend. The Laplace trend test is used to verify whether there is an improving or deteriorating trend (Bohoris, 1996, pp. 18-28). The Laplace trend test is given by:

$$Z_{Laplace} = \sqrt{12r} \left(\sum_{i=1}^r \left(T_i - \frac{T_{end}}{2} \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

The result for the calculation under equation (10) is $Z_{obs} = 3.38$ where the theoretical value is $Z_{0.95} = 1.65$. There is a significant decreasing trend for the Gini coefficient using the period between 2004 and 2013 as the basis. This finding suggests that there is a positive prospect for the ASEAN countries because the income gap among the 10 countries significantly decreases.

4.4 Weibull Analysis for the AEC's System Failure Forecast

Although the finding from the Laplace trend test shows that there is a significant reduction trend narrowing the Gini coefficient gap among the ASEAN countries, further question must be asked: what is the probability that such a gap-closing trend will continue to occur? In order to answer this question, it is necessary to engage the Weibull test.

The Weibull test is a tool to predict failure. With a series of observation of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n where each observation is observed in discrete time t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n such that the event series observed is in a form $((x_1 : t_1), (x_2 : t_1), \dots, (x_n : t_1))$. This series of events is compared to the expected standard below which is considered as failure. Call that expected value \hat{x} . The time failure may be created by the following conditions: (i) if the sample size is less than 100, use the following formula:

$$F(t) = \frac{(i + 0.30)}{(n + 0.40)} \quad (11)$$

where i = the i^{th} number of event in $((x_1 : t_1), (x_2 : t_1), \dots, (x_n : t_1))$ and n = sample size.

As part of the Weibull distribution test, it is necessary to general the XY arrays for the Weibull distribution. Recall that the series $((x_1 : t_1), (x_2 : t_1), \dots, (x_n : t_1))$ are observed events. To make sense of these observations in terms of failure rate, it is necessary to generate the Weibull plot to obtain the values for X and Y in order to run a regression for the Weibull distribution. The X-array may be generated by the following formula:

$$X_i = \ln \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - F(t)} \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

Thus from the observations series $((x_1 : t_1), (x_2 : t_1), \dots, (x_n : t_1))$, a separate array of X_i is generated to correspond with each i in $((x_1 : t_1), (x_2 : t_1), \dots, (x_n : t_1))$. With known X_i , the dependent Y_i array is generated by

$$Y_i = \ln(x_i) \quad (13)$$

With two arrays generated by (11) and (12), it is possible to run a Weibull regression from known Weibull plot:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} x_1 : t_1 \rightarrow X_1 \\ x_2 : t_2 \rightarrow X_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n : t_n \rightarrow X_n \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow X_i = \ln \left(\ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - F(t)} \right) \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \left. \begin{array}{l} x_1 : t_1 \rightarrow Y_1 \\ x_2 : t_2 \rightarrow Y_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_n : t_n \rightarrow Y_n \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow \ln(x_i)$$

From the above arrays, a linear regression equation in a form of $Y_w = a + bX$ may be derived. In this case, the Weibull linear equation for the Gini coefficient trend is $Y_w = -0.41 + 0.021X$ with the coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0.89$. Other relevant Weibull statistics include: $\beta = -47.34$, $\eta = 0.67$; and the Weibull reliability is $R_w = 0.37$. The Weibull reliability measures the reliability of the system; in this case, it is 37% reliable or the probability that the Gini coefficient gap will close is 37%. The finding under the Laplace's formula is also confirmed by Weibull's beta. In Weibull statistics, if the value of beta is less than zero, it means that the failure (Gini coefficient gap) is decreasing (gap closing) in the following periods: $t_i : (t_{n+1}, \dots, T_N)$. The Weibull's eta value indicates the level of failure at the Y-intercept. In this case, eta is 0.67.

The finding under Weibull system failure analysis suggests that there is a decreasing trend in Gini coefficient; the gap in income distribution will narrow in relations with time. Out of the various factors examined as the indicator for economic identity for the AEC, the decreasing trend of the Gini coefficient appears to provide a common ground upon which all countries could agree. As a common market and an economic community, this finding is an important indicator that there is a commonality for which the 10 countries could look to as a shared identity in the new economy.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This research presents the concept of economic identity for the ASEAN countries. Four factors were used as the indicators for economic identities: per capita GDP, GDP growth rate, HDI and Gini Coefficient. Among these four factors, it was found there only the Gini coefficient trend show evidence of homogeneity among the group. On the basis of per capita GDP, GDP growth, and HDI, the ASEAN countries are economically heterogenous; however, as a group both group1 and group2 are homogenous. On individual country basis, this heterogeneity would present greater challenge for the ASEAN members to achieve the AEC's shared ideal of "one vision, one identity, one community." However, as a group the ASEAN may integrate well. The intended contribution of this research is to provide practical assessment of the claim of shared identity among the ASEAN countries on the basis of economic indicators. The 10 countries are economically diverse. This economic diversity will hinder the prospect of smooth transition into a common market under the aegis of the AEC. In economic terms, the ASEAN lacks shared identity.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, Dallas W.; Kish, Leslie; Cornell, Richard G. (1980). "On Stratification, Grouping and Matching." *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics* (Blackwell Publishing) 7 (2): 61–66.
- Athena S. Leoussi, Steven Grosby (2006). *Nationalism and Ethnosymbolism: History, Culture and Ethnicity in the Formation of Nations*, Edinburgh University Press, 2006, p. 115.
- Bassein, A. (1996). "A Sampler of Randomness." *Amer. Math. Monthly* 103, 483-490.
- Beyer, W. H. (1987). *CRC Standard Mathematical Tables, 28th ed.* Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, pp. 491-492.
- Bohoris, G.A. (1996), "A trend testing in reliability engineering." *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, Vol. 13, No.6, pp.18-28.

- Dagum, C. (1980). "The Generation and Distribution of Income, the Lorenz Curve and the Gini Ratio." *Écon. Appl.* **33**, 327-367.
- Damgaard, C. and Weiner, J. (2000). "Describing Inequality in Plant Size or Fecundity." *Ecology* **81**, 1139-1142.
- Davies, A.; Quinlivan, G. (2006). "A Panel Data Analysis of the Impact of Trade on Human Development." *Journal of Socio-Economics* **35** (5): 868–876.
- Dixon, P. M.; Weiner, J.; Mitchell-Olds, T.; and Woodley, R. (1987). "Bootstrapping the Gini Coefficient of Inequality." *Ecology* **68**, 1548-1551.
- Dixon, P. M.; Weiner, J.; Mitchell-Olds, T.; and Woodley, R. (1988). "Erratum to 'Bootstrapping the Gini Coefficient of Inequality.'" *Ecology* **69**, 1307.
- Gini, C. (1912). "Variabilità e mutabilità." Reprinted in *Memorie di metodologia statistica* (Ed. E. Pizetti and T. Salvemini.) Rome: Libreria Eredi Virgilio Veschi, 1955.
- Hart, B.I. (1942). "Significance Level for the Mean Square Successive Difference to the Variance." *Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, **13**: 445-7.
- Lorenz, M. O. (1905). "Methods for Measuring the Concentration of Wealth." *Amer. Stat. Assoc.* **9**, 209-219.
- Glasser, G. J. (1962). "Variance Formulas for the Mean Difference and Coefficient of Concentration." *J. Amer. Stat. Assoc.* **57**, 648-654.
- Goulden, C. H. (1956). *Methods of Statistical Analysis, 2nd ed.* New York: Wiley, pp. 50-55.
- Höpner, Martin and Schäfer, Armin (2012). Integration among Unequals: How the Heterogeneity of European Varieties of Capitalism Shapes the Social and Democratic Potential of the EU." Discussion Paper No. 12/5. Max Planck Institute for the Study of Societies, Cologne, Germany. July 2012. ISSN 0944-2073 (print). ISSN 1864-4325 (online).
- Kupper, Lawrence L.; Karon, John M.; Kleinbaum, David G.; Morgenstern, Hal; Lewis, Donald K. (1981). "Matching in Epidemiologic Studies: Validity and Efficiency Considerations." *Biometrics* (International Biometric Society) **37** (2): 271–291.
- Lee, Yoonmi (2000). *Modern Education, Textbooks, and the Image of the Nation: Politics and Modernization and Nationalism in Korean Education: 1880-1910*. Routledge (published 2012). p. 29. ISBN 9781136600791.
- McGillivray, Mark; White, Howard (2006). "Measuring development? The UNDP's human development index." *Journal of International Development* **5**(2): 183–192.
- Miller, David (1995). *On Nationality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. ISBN 0-19-828047-5.
- O'Sullivan, Arthur; Sheffrin, Steven M. (2003). *Economics: Principles in action*. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey 07458: Pearson Prentice Hall. pp. 197, 507. ISBN 0-13-063085-3.
- Press, W. H.; Flannery, B. P.; Teukolsky, S. A.; and Vetterling, W. T. (1992). *Numerical Recipes in FORTRAN: The Art of Scientific Computing, 2nd ed.* Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, p. 621.
- Rothi, Despina et al. (2005). National attachment and patriotism in a European nation: A British study. *Political Psychology*, **26**, 135 - 155.
- Rubin, Donald B. (1973). "Matching to Remove Bias in Observational Studies." *Biometrics*(International Biometric Society) **29** (1): 159–183.
- Sen, A. (1973). *On Economic Inequality*. Oxford, England: Clarendon Press.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In W. G. Austin & S. Worchel (Eds.), *The social psychology of intergroup relations* (pp. 33–47). Monterey, CA: Brooks/Cole.
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1986). The social identity theory of intergroup behaviour. In S. Worchel & W. G. Austin (Eds.), *Psychology of Intergroup Relations* (pp. 7–24). Chicago, IL: Nelson-Hall.

- Turner, John; Oakes, Penny (1986). “The significance of the social identity concept for social psychology with reference to individualism, interactionism and social influence.” *British Journal of Social Psychology* **25** (3): 237–252.
- Turner, J. C. (1999). “Some current issues in research on social identity and self-categorization theories.” In Ellemers, N.; Spears, R.; Doosje, B. *Social identity* (Oxford: Blackwell): 6–34.
- Wallman, S. (1977). “Ethnicity research in Britain,” *Current Anthropology*, v. 18, n. 3, pp. 531–532.
- Weiner, J. and Solbrig, O. T. (1984). “The Meaning and Measurement of Size Hierarchies in Plant Populations.” *Oecologia* **61**, 334-336.

APPENDIX 1

Theoretical Value for Anderson-Darling Test for Normal Distribution

Case 1:

The mean μ is unknown and is estimated by \bar{X} , but population variance σ^2 is known. The Z is estimated by:

$$Z_1 = \frac{X_{(i)} - \bar{X}}{\sigma}$$

Case 2:

The mean μ is known, and the population variance σ^2 is estimated by $S^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})^2$. The

Z is estimated by:

$$Z_2 = \frac{X_{(i)} - \mu}{S_1}$$

Case 3:

Both parameters are unknown and are estimated by \bar{X} and $S^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_i (X_i - \bar{X})^2$

$$Z_3 = \frac{X_{(i)} - \bar{X}}{S}$$

Cases	Sample size	0.05	0.025	0.01
All cases	≥ 5	2.492	3.070	3.853
Case 1	≥ 5	1.087	1.285	1.551
Case 2	≥ 5	2.308	2.898	3.702
Case 3	≥ 5	0.752	0.875	1.035

Adapted from Tables 1, 2 & 3 in Stephen, M.A. (1979). "The Anderson-Darling Statistic." Technical Report No. 39, Oct. 31, 1979.

APPENDIX 2
Determining pValue

The observed T value could be converted to the Z score manually in three steps. Firstly, convert T to X by $X = 1.15T$. Secondly, insert X into the equation $Z = (X - 1.64) + 1.98 - 0.004n - 0.06$ where n is the sample size. Lastly, with known Z, obtained the pValue where $pValue = 1 - F(Z)$; thus:

$$F(Z) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\sqrt{\pi}(\beta_1 Z^5 + \beta_2 Z^3 + \beta_3 Z))}$$

where $\beta_1 = 0.0004406$, $\beta_2 = 0.0418198$, and $\beta_3 = 0.90000000$.

$Z = (X - 1.64) + 1.98 - 0.004N - 0.06$, and $X = 1.115T$.